

Thermo-tolerant and Thermo-Sensitive Characterization of Selected Okra Genotypes at Seedling Stage

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Abstract

Twenty different okra genotypes were screened out at seedling stage under different temperature regimes (25 °C (control), 40 °C and 45 °C) to categorize them as thermo-tolerant and thermo-sensitive. On the basis of morphological, physiological, gasses exchange, enzymatic and ionic characteristics thermo-tolerant and as thermo-sensitive okra genotypes were identified. The results revealed that heat stress caused a significant reduction in morphological (root/shoot length, plant fresh/dry weight, leaf area) and physiological attributes (photosynthesis, stomatal conductance, transpiration rate) in both thermo-tolerant and thermo-sensitive okra genotypes. Whereas, thermo-tolerant genotypes showed less reduction in morphological and physiological attributes as compared to thermo-sensitive and vice versa. Antioxidant osmolytes (proline, glycine betaine) and enzyme enzymes (superoxide dismutase, peroxidase) activities in root/shoot indicated that thermo-tolerant genotypes had the highest heat tolerance potential as they showed the greater increase in antioxidant enzyme and osmolytes activities as compared to the thermo-sensitive genotypes. Ionic attributes (calcium and magnesium) were least affected in thermo-tolerant genotypes whereas this trend was opposite for thermo-sensitive okra genotypes. Overall, it was concluded that heat/ high-temperature stress is very drastic for growth and development of okra genotypes at seedling stage and based upon cluster analysis membership genotypes Kiran-51, Punjab selection, Ikra-1, Sarsabaz, Sanum, Pen beauty, Sabaz pari and Green wonder were categorized as thermo-tolerant whereas, Shehzadi, Lush green, OK-1307, Anarkali and OK-1305 were moderate-tolerant, while Ikra-3, MF-03, Okra-7100, Cick-576, Pusa sawani, Okra-3, and Ikra-2 were categorized as thermo-sensitive okra genotypes.

Keywords: Heat stress, Okra, Seedling, Screening, Thermo-tolerant, Thermo-sensitive

Introduction

Worldwide, the major concern for crop production is high-temperature stress, as it adversely affects plant growth, development, and productivity. In order to understand the plant response and adaptation under high-temperature stress, understanding of mechanisms underlying increased thermotolerance of plants is required. Plant responses and adaptation to high temperature vary across and within the species; it also varies at different developmental stages of the plant (Bita and Gerats, 2013). Plants accumulate metabolites osmoprotectants, heat shock proteins, antioxidants, etc. as a result of high temperature stress conditions and modifications in metabolic pathways (Xiong and Zhu, 2002). These modifications enhance the significance of physiological, molecular, and biological studies of plants to expose the biological activities as a result of heat stress responses. These studies will also be useful for the development of crop varieties adapted to high temperature stress conditions (Hemantaranjan *et al.*, 2014).

High temperature stress results in scorching, abscission, and senescence of leaves and stems, inhibits shoot and root growth, damage fruit and eventually reduced quality and productivity of plants (Bita and Gerats, 2013). High temperatures beyond a critical threshold enhance the production of reactive oxygen species in plants, which damages the membranes and degrade proteins, lipids, and other bio-molecules, bringing about a detrimental change in the metabolism (Anjum *et al.*, 2014). Tolerance to heat-stress involves several mechanisms like, synthesis of heat shock proteins, compatible osmolytes, factors that regulate membrane fluidity, activation of the antioxidative systems to scavenge the reactive oxygen species, etc. (Kumar *et al.*, 2012). The plant's antioxidant defense system consists of the enzymes such as superoxide dismutase, catalase, peroxidase, ascorbate peroxidase, glutathione reductase and glutathione peroxidase along with non enzymatic components such as compatible solutes, reduced glutathione and ascorbic acid (Anjum *et al.*, 2014,2017).

Okra is a famous crop of tropical and subtropical areas. It belongs to the family Malvaceae. The temperatures of more than 20°C is considered as important for normal growth, development and productivity of okra (Abd El-Kader *et al.*, 2010; Lamont, 1999). While, the optimum temperature for ideal growth and production of okra lies under 20-30°C, with

least temperatures requirement of 18°C and a maximum of 35°C (Benchasri, 2012). In the present study, the emphasis was to categorize available okra germplasm for heat tolerant and heat sensitive by using various stress measuring indexes at seedling stage. This will explore the new horizons to identify thermo-tolerant germplasm of okra available in Pakistan to get its good yield for a longer period of time in the summer season.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted in growth chambers of the Department of Horticulture, University College of Agriculture, University of Sargodha, Punjab, Pakistan. Seeds of twenty okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L. (Moench.)) genotypes (Sabazpari, Sarsabaz, Pen beauty, Green wonder, Punjab selection, Anarkali, Shehzadi, Ikra-3, Ikra-1, Kiran-51, Okra-7100, Sanum, Lush green, Ikra-2, OK-1305, OK-1307, Pusasawani, MF-03, Okra-3 and Click-5769) were collected from Ayyub Agriculture Research Institute (AARI), Faisalabad and National Agricultural Research Council (NARC), Islamabad. Disinfected seeds with 5% sodium hypochlorite solution followed by repeated washing with double distilled water were sown in plastic pots filled with peat moss (Sia Pindstrup Ltd., Talsi, Latvia). Half strength Hoagland solution was applied as a nutrition source. The plants were irrigated as per requirement by observing the moisture of rooting media. Three growth chambers were adjusted to 25/23 °C 40/28 °C and 45/28 °C day/night temperature respectively with 65% relative humidity, light intensity 550 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ from fluorescent tube lights, photoperiod 11.5 hours during the whole period of the experiment. Fifteen days after germination, plants were exposed to 25/23 °C (control) 40/28 °C and 45/28 °C \pm 0.5/0.3 day/night temperature in respective growth chambers. One week after induction of heat-stress the data regarding various morphological and physiological characteristics were recorded through the appropriate standard procedure.

Seeds disinfected with 10% sodium hypochlorite were grown in Petri dishes on Whatman filter paper (50 seeds per petri dish) wetted with double distilled water. The treatments were replicated five times and place in a growth chamber at 25 °C, 40 °C and 45 °C. Germination was calculated for seven days. The germination percentage was calculated as follows

$$\text{Germination percentage} = (\text{Number of seeds germinated} / \text{Total number of seeds sown}) \times 100$$

Data was collected for the seedling stage after 35 days of seed sowing. Root and shoot length of plants samples was measured in centimeters (cm) through meter rod. Following measurement of root and shoot length, the plant samples were placed on a digital balance to measure plants fresh weight. After that plant samples were oven dried (Memmert-110, Schawabach, Germany) at 72 °C for 48 h, and the average dry weight of each replication was recorded. The leaf area was calculated using leaf area meter (LI-3100; LI-COR Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA). A fully expanded youngest leaf of each plant (the second leaf from top) was used to measure the gases exchange characteristics like transpiration rate (E), photosynthetic rate (Pn) and stomatal conductance (gs) by using photosynthesis measuring-system CI-340 portable infrared gas analyzer (Analytical Development Company, Hoddesdon, England).

The proline contents were calculated following the method of Bates et al. (1973). Glycinebetaine contents were measured as described by Grieve and Grattan (1983). Whereas, for the estimation of Ca and Mg contents, plant material was digested, for this purpose dried ground plant material (0.5 g) was digested in concentrated sulphuric acid (5 mL) in digestion tubes as described by Wolf (1990). The digestion tubes were allowed to incubate overnight at room temperature. After the incubation process H₂O₂ (35% @ 0.5 mL per test tube was added and the tubes were shifted in a digestion block and constantly heated to 350 °C) until the fumes were formed. After the appearance of fumes, the digestion tubes were more heated for half an hour. The digestion tubes were separated from the digestion block and allowed to cool for five minutes. After cooling again, H₂O₂ (0.5 mL) was dropped gently in the tubes and replaced in digestion block. This step was repeated sporadically until the digested material become colorless. The digested material was filtered, and its volume was raised to 50 mL in a volumetric flask. The filtered digested was used for the estimation of Ca and Mg through titration against EDTA solution (0.01 N) as a standard solution using EBI and calcon indicators as described in US-Staff Hand Book-60 (1962).

Results of the tested parameters were described on the basis of percent increase/decrease with respect to their respective control using the following formula.

$$\% \text{ Increase/decrease} = \frac{\text{Value observed at control} - \text{Value observed at high temperature}}{\text{Value observed at control}} \times 100$$

The experiment was laid out under two factorial completely randomized design (CRD) arrangements with five replications. There were five pots per replicate. The data was analyzed by standard statistical procedures as described by Gomez and Gomez (1984). Tukey HSD test was used to evaluate the significance of differences between the treatments

at $P < 0.05$ ($n = 5$). Data were analyzed using the statistical package Statistics 8.1.

Results

Morphological characteristics of thermo-tolerant and as thermo-sensitive okra genotypes

The greater germination percentage (81.32 %) was observed in plants grown under control (25 °C) whereas germination percentage was reduced with increasing levels of heat stress. Among the heat levels, the highest germination percentage (66.80 %) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (54.19 %) (Table 1). Average decrease in germination percentage was observed higher in Click-5769 (31.36 %), Okra-3 (30.28 %), Ikra-2 (29.77 %) and Ikra-3 (29.49 %). Whereas, genotypes Sabazpari (18.25 %), Green wonder (19.55 %), Punjab selection (20.13 %) and Pen beauty (20.55 %) were least affected by heat stress (Table 1).

The highest shoot length (15.85 cm) was observed in plants grown under 25 °C (control) whereas, among the heat levels highest shoot length (12.51 cm) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (10.01 cm) (Table 1). Average decrease in shoot length was observed higher in Okra-3 (40.36 %), Ikra-2 (38.85 %), Click-5769 (38.25 %) and Pusasawani (37.55 %). Whereas, genotypes Sabazpari (21.72 %), Punjab selection (22.15 %), Green wonder (22.48 %), and Pen beauty (23.08 %) were least affected by heat stress and exhibited a minimum reduction in shoot length as compared to other tested okra genotypes (Table 1).

At 25 °C (control) greater root length (8.10 cm) was observed as compared to the plants grown under heat stress. Whereas, among the heat stressed plants the highest root length (6.45 cm) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (5.23 cm) (Table 2). Average decrease in root length was observed higher in Ikra-2 (38.66 %), Okra-3 (37.89 %), Click-5769 (37.16 %) and Pusasawani (36.40 %). Whereas, genotypes Punjab selection (20.31 %), Sabazpari (20.94 %), Pen beauty (22.10 %) and Sarsabaz (22.67 %) were least affected by heat stress as they exhibited a minimum reduction in root length as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 2).

The greater plant fresh weight (58.61 g) was observed in plants grown under control (25 °C) whereas, among the heat levels highest plant fresh weight (44.13 g) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (33.36 g) (Table 2). At 40 °C highest reduction in plant fresh weight was noted in Okra-3 (30.68 %), Ikra-2 (29.98 %), Click-5769 (29.42 %) and MF-03 (29.24 %). Whereas, at 45 °C maximum percent decrease in plant fresh weight was observed in Okra-3 (51.95 %), Ikra-2 (50.98 %), Click-5769 (50.19 %) and MF-03 (49.93 %) (Table 2). Average decrease in plant fresh weight was observed higher in Okra-3 (41.31 %), Ikra-2 (40.48 %), Click-5769 (39.80 %) and Okra-7100 (39.15 %). Whereas, genotypes Sabazpari (27.33 %), Punjab selection (28.22 %), Green wonder (28.66 %), and Sarsabaz (30.54 %) were least affected by heat stress as they exhibited a minimum reduction in fresh plant weight as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 2).

Highest plant dry weight (7.62 g) was observed in plants grown under 25 °C (control) whereas, plant dry weight was lowest under different levels of heat stress. Among the heat levels, highest plant dry weight (5.92 g) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (5.12 g) (Table 3). At 40 °C data showed that lowest reduction in plant dry weight was noted in Punjab selection (16.29 %), Sabazpari (16.94 %), Green wonder (17.51 %) and Sarsabaz (17.97 %) (Table 3). whereas, the evaluation of genotypes at 45 °C indicated maximum % decrease in plant dry weight in Okra-3 (42.57 %), Ikra-2 (42.02 %), Click-5769 (41.62 %) and MF-03 (41.15 %) (Table 3). Average decrease in plant dry weight was observed higher in Okra-3 (35.75 %), Ikra-2 (35.32 %), Click-5769 (34.94 %) and Okra-7100 (33.89 %). Whereas, genotypes Punjab selection (20.17 %), Sabazpari (20.67 %), Green wonder (21.60 %) and Sarsabaz (22.14 %) were least affected by heat stress as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 3).

The greater numbers of leaves per plant (5.24) were observed in plants grown at 25 °C (control) whereas, the number of leaves per plant was reduced with an increase in heat stress levels. Among the heat levels, highest numbers of leaves per plant (4.11) were observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (3.30) (Table 3). Data regarding a number of leaves per plant revealed that at 40 °C highest reduction in the number of leaves per plant was noted in Click-5769 (28.22 %), Okra-3 (27.46 %), Ikra-2 (27.15 %) and Ikra-3 (25.79 %). On the other hand, lowest reduction in numbers of leaves per plant was observed in Sabazpari (30.54 %), Green wonder (30.85 %), Anarkali (31.74 %) and Kiran-51 (32.32 %) at 45 °C as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 3). Average decrease in number of leaves per plant was observed higher in Click-5769 (37.14 %), Okra-3 (36.29 %), Ikra-2 (35.50 %) and Ikra-3 (34.52 %). Whereas, genotypes Sabazpari (23.94 %), Green wonder (24.21 %), Anarkali (24.93 %) and Kiran-51 (25.28 %) were least affected by heat stress as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 3).

The greater leaf area (14.95cm²) was observed in plants grown under control (25 °C) whereas, leaf area was reduced under heat stress. Among the heat levels the highest leaf area (12.10 cm²) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (10.44 cm²) (Table 4). Data regarding leaf area revealed that at 40 °C the lowest reduction in leaf area was observed in

Sabazpari (14.89 %), Green wonder (15.53 %), Punjab selection (15.95 %) and Pen beauty (16.27 %). The comparison among genotypes at 45 °C indicated that maximum percent decrease in leaf area was observed in Click-5769 (38.14 %), Okra-3 (37.12 %), Ikra-2 (36.51%) and Ikra-3 (36.12 %). (Table 4). Average decrease in leaf area was observed higher in Click-5769 (31.36 %), Okra-3 (30.28 %), Ikra-2 (29.77 %) and Ikra-3 (29.49 %). Whereas, genotypes Sabazpari (18.25 %), Green wonder (19.55 %), Punjab selection (20.13 %) and Pen beauty (20.55 %) were least affected by heat stress as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 4).

Physiological characteristics of thermo-tolerant and as thermo-sensitive okra genotypes under high temperature stress

The highest transpiration rate ($1.94 \text{ mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$) was observed in plants grown under 25 °C (control) whereas, the lowest transpiration rate was observed under heat stress. Among the heat levels, the highest transpiration rate ($1.47 \text{ mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C ($1.36 \text{ mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$) (Table 4). Transpiration rate at 40 °C reduced less in Sabazpari (17.89 %), Ikra-1 (18.89 %), Kiran-51 (19.66 %) and Green wonder (19.85 %). Whereas, under 45 °C genotypes Click-5769 (35.56 %), MF-03 (34.46 %), Ikra-2 (33.65 %) and OK-1305 (33.37 %) exhibited maximum reduction in transpiration rate and were more affected by heat stress as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 4). The average reduction in transpiration rate was observed lowest in Sabazpari (22.15 %), Green wonder (22.27 %), Kiran-51 (23.08 %) and Ikra-1 (23.82 %). Whereas, Click-5769 (33.72 %), MF-03 (32.61 %), Ikra-3 (31.43 %) and Ikra-2 (31.27 %) were affected greater by heat stress as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 4).

At 25 °C (control) greater photosynthesis rate ($20.93 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$) was observed as compared to the plants grown under heat stress. Among the heat stressed plants greater photosynthesis rate ($16.77 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C ($13.57 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$) (Table 5). Percent reduction in photosynthesis rate was observed greater in Okra-3 (25.93 %), Ikra-2 (25.62 %), Click-5769 (25.13 %) and MF-03 (24.86 %) at 40 °C whereas it was observed lowest in Sabazpari (28.83 %), Punjab selection (29.27 %), Green wonder (29.96 %) and Sarsabaz (31.26 %) at 45 °C as compared to remaining okra genotypes (Table 5). Under different levels of heat stress, the average reduction in photosynthesis rate was observed less in Sabazpari (22.43 %), Punjab selection (22.68 %), Green wonder (23.39 %) and Sarsabaz (24.26 %). Whereas, Okra-3 (34.79 %), Ikra-2 (34.41 %), Click-5769 (33.87 %) and MF-03 (33.45 %) was more affected by heat stress as they exhibited a greater reduction in photosynthesis rate as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 5).

The greater stomatal conductance ($62.03 \text{ mmol m}^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$) was observed in plants grown under control (25 °C) whereas among the heat levels highest stomatal conductance ($49.41 \text{ mmol m}^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C ($39.66 \text{ mmol m}^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$) (Table 5). Data regarding stomatal conductance revealed that at 40 °C highest reduction in stomatal conductance was noted in Click-5769 (24.93 %) Okra-3 (24.62 %), Ikra-2 (24.25 %), and MF-03 (23.86 %). Whereas, the lowest reduction in stomatal conductance was observed in Sabazpari (27.34 %), Green wonder (27.86 %), Punjab selection (28.37 %) and Pen beauty (29.08 %) as compared to rest of okra genotypes at 45 °C (Table 5). Under different levels of heat stress, the average reduction in stomatal conductance was observed lowest in Sabazpari (21.64 %), Green wonder (22.07 %), Punjab selection (22.44 %) and Pen beauty (23.02 %). Whereas, Click-5769 (35.77 %), Okra-3 (34.77 %), Ikra-2 (34.28 %), and Ikra-3 (33.70 %) were more affected by heat stress and exhibited a greater reduction in stomatal conductance as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 5).

Antioxidant osmolytes and enzyme enzymes characteristics of thermo-tolerant and as thermo-sensitive okra genotypes under high temperature stress

The lowest leaf proline contents ($1.41 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{ FW}$) were observed in plants grown at 25 °C (control) whereas; leaf proline contents were increased with increase in heat stress levels. Among the heat levels, the highest leaf proline contents ($1.60 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{ FW}$) were observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C ($1.70 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{ FW}$) (Table 6). Data regarding leaf proline contents revealed that at 40 °C highest increase in leaf proline contents was noted in Sabazpari (17.84 %), Green wonder (16.64 %), Punjab selection (15.94 %) and Kiran-51 (15.38 %). Whereas, the lowest increase in leaf proline contents was observed in Click-5769, Ikra-2 (16.90 %), Okra-3 (17.37 %), and Ikra-3 (18.76 %) at 45 °C. (Table 6). The average increase in leaf proline contents under different levels of heat stress was noted greater in Sabazpari (21.87 %), Green wonder (20.51 %), Punjab selection (19.38 %) and Kiran-51 (18.81 %). Whereas, Click-5769 (13.07 %), Ikra-2 (13.62 %), Okra-3 (14.08 %), and Ikra-3 (15.43 %) exhibited less increase in leaf proline contents as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 6).

The minimum root proline contents ($1.02 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{ FW}$) was observed in plants grown under control (25 °C) whereas, among the heat levels highest root proline contents ($1.16 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{ FW}$) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C ($1.23 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{ FW}$) (Table 6). Data regarding root proline contents revealed that at 40 °C highest percent increase in root

proline contents was noted in Sabazpari (15.98 %), Green wonder (15.56 %), Punjab selection (15.07) and Kiran-51 (14.74 %). Whereas, at 45 °C genotypes Click-5769 (16.08 %), Ikra-2 (16.94 %), Okra-3 (17.41 %) and Ikra-3 (18.10 %) showed less increase in root proline contents as compared to remaining okra genotypes (Table 6). Average jump in root proline content under heat stress was observed higher in Sabazpari (21.19 %), Green wonder (20.51 %), Punjab selection (19.72) and Kiran-51 (19.12 %). Whereas, genotypes Click-5769 (13.43 %), Ikra-2 (14.14 %), Okra-3 (14.49 %) and Ikra-3 (15.11 %) expressed less increase in root proline contents as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 6).

Leaf glycinebetaine contents were observed lowest ($1.69 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ FW) in plants grown under control (25 °C) whereas among the heat levels highest leaf glycinebetaine contents ($1.97 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ FW) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C ($2.10 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ FW) (Table 7). Data regarding leaf glycinebetaine contents revealed that at 40 °C Sabazpari (19.58 %), Punjab selection (19.16 %), Green wonder (19.07 %) and Sarsabaz (18.74 %) showed the highest increase in leaf glycinebetaine contents. Whereas, it was observed lowest in Click-5769 (18.65 %), Ikra-2 (19.04 %), MF-03 (19.15 %) and Okra-3 (19.22 %) at 45 °C as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 7). Average increase in leaf glycinebetaine contents was observed lowest in Click-5769 (15.70 %), MF-03 (16.14 %), Ikra-2 (16.19 %) and Okra-3 (16.50 %). The genotypes Sabazpari (24.96 %), Punjab selection (24.26 %), Green wonder (23.88 %) and Sarsabaz (23.28 %) exhibited a greater increase in leaf glycinebetaine contents as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 7).

The lowest root glycinebetaine contents ($0.99 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ FW) was observed in plants grown under 25 °C (control) whereas, among the heat levels greater root glycinebetaine contents ($1.11 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ FW) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C ($1.18 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ FW) (Table 7). Root glycinebetaine contents at 40 °C increased greater in Sabazpari (14.72 %), Green wonder (14.16 %), Punjab selection (14.05 %) and Pen beauty (13.89 %). Whereas, at 45 °C genotypes Click-5769 (16.73 %), Okra-3 (16.89 %), Ikra-2 (17.46 %) and Ikra-3 (17.73 %) exhibited less increase in root glycinebetaine contents as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 7). The average increase in root glycinebetaine contents was observed higher in Sabazpari (18.64 %), Green wonder (17.95 %), Punjab selection (17.43 %) and Pen beauty (17.27 %). Whereas, Click-5769 (13.45 %), Ikra-2 (14.17 %), Ikra-3 (14.43 %) and Okra-7100 (14.58 %) exhibited less increase in root glycinebetaine contents as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 7).

Lowest leaf SOD contents (6.98units mg^{-1} protein) were observed in plants grown at 25 °C (control) whereas among the heat levels highest leaf SOD contents (7.76units mg^{-1} protein) were observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (8.34units mg^{-1} protein) (Table 8). Data regarding leaf SOD contents revealed that at 40 °C highest increase in leaf SOD contents was noted in Sabazpari (14.91 %), Green wonder (14.35 %), Punjab selection (13.93 %) and Kiran-51 (13.01 %). Whereas, On the other hand, at 45 °C lowest increase in leaf SOD contents was observed in Click-5769 (14.03 %), Ikra-2 (14.67 %), Okra-3 (14.78 %), and Ikra-3 (15.13 %) (Table 8). The average increase in leaf SOD contents under different levels of heat stress was noted greater in Sabazpari (20.93 %), Green wonder (20.26 %), Punjab selection (19.58 %) and Kiran-51 (18.29 %). Whereas, Click-5769 (11.10 %), Ikra-2 (11.61 %), Okra-3 (11.72 %), and Ikra-3 (11.97 %) exhibited less increase in leaf SOD contents as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 8).

The minimum root SOD contents (3.72 units mg^{-1} protein) was observed in plants grown under control (25 °C) whereas, among the heat levels highest root SOD contents (4.15 units mg^{-1} protein) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (4.49 units mg^{-1} protein) (Table 8). Data regarding root SOD contents revealed that at 40 °C highest percent increase in root SOD contents was noted in Sabazpari (15.31 %), Green wonder (14.65 %), Punjab selection (14.09 %) and Kiran-51 (13.69 %). On the other hand, at 45 °C genotypes Click-5769 (15.46 %), Ikra-2 (16.29 %), Okra-3 (16.41 %) and Ikra-3 (16.95 %) showed less increase in root SOD contents as compared to remaining okra genotypes (Table 8). The average rise in root SOD contents under heat stress was observed higher in Sabazpari (21.26 %), Green wonder (20.46 %), Punjab selection (19.65) and Kiran-51 (19.08 %). Whereas, genotypes Click-5769 (11.87 %), Ikra-2 (12.67 %), Okra-3 (12.79 %) and Ikra-3 (13.31 %) and were more affected by heat stress as they expressed less increase in root SOD contents as compared to rest of okra genotypes. (Table 8).

Leaf POD contents were observed lowest (0.109 units mg^{-1} protein) in plants grown under control (25 °C) whereas among the heat levels highest leaf POD contents (0.123 units mg^{-1} protein) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (0.132units mg^{-1} protein) (Table 9). Data regarding leaf POD contents revealed that at 40 °C Sabazpari (15.91 %), Punjab selection (15.27 %), Green wonder (15.66 %) and Kiran-51 (14.78 %) showed the highest increase in leaf POD contents. Whereas, at 45 °C it was observed lowest in Click-5769 (16.41 %), Ikra-2 (17.13 %) Okra-3 (17.38 %) and Ikra-3 (18.10 %) as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 9). Average increase in leaf POD contents was observed lowest in Click-5769 (15.70 %), MF-03 (16.14 %), Ikra-2 (16.19 %) and Okra-3 (16.50 %). The genotypes Sabazpari (24.96 %), Punjab selection (24.26 %), Green wonder (23.88 %) and Sarsabaz (23.28 %) were least affected by heat stress as they exhibited a greater increase in leaf POD contents as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 9).

Root POD contents were observed lowest (0.059 units mg^{-1} protein) in plants grown under 25 °C (control) whereas among the heat levels greater root POD contents (0.068 units mg^{-1} protein) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (0.072 units mg^{-1} protein) (Table 9). Root POD contents at 40 °C increased greater in Sabazpari (16.77 %), Green wonder (16.55 %), Punjab selection (16.19 %) and Kiran-51 (15.84 %). On the other hand, at 45 °C genotypes Okra-03 (16.98 %), Ikra-2 (17.04 %), Click-5769 (17.50 %) and Ikra-3 (18.08 %) exhibited less increase in root POD contents as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 9). Average increase in root POD contents was observed higher in Sabazpari (22.09 %), Green wonder (21.54 %), Punjab selection (20.88 %) and Kiran-51 (20.27 %). Whereas, Ikra-2 (14.24 %), Okra-3 (14.29 %), Click-5769 (14.59 %) and Ikra-3 (15.09 %) exhibited less increase in root POD contents as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 9).

Ionic characteristics of thermo-tolerant and as thermo-sensitive okra genotypes under high temperature stress

The highest calcium contents (0.82 ppm) was observed in plants grown under 25 °C (control) whereas among the heat levels highest calcium contents (0.66 ppm) was observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (0.53 ppm) (Table 10). At 40 °C data regarding calcium contents showed that highest reduction in calcium contents was noted in Ikra-2 (23.93 %), Okra-3 (23.62 %), Click-5769 (23.35 %) and Pusasawani (22.86 %). Whereas at 45 °C genotypes Green wonder (29.00 %), Punjab selection (31.83 %), Sabazpari (32.20 %) and Sarsabaz (32.29 %) exhibited the lowest reduction in calcium contents percentage as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 10). Average decrease in calcium contents was observed higher in Ikra-2 (31.37 %), Okra-3 (31.10 %), Click-5769 (30.85 %) and Pusasawani (30.41 %). Whereas, genotypes Green wonder (23.42 %), Punjab selection (23.53 %), Sabazpari (23.95 %), and Sarsabaz (24.05 %) exhibited minimum reduction in calcium contents as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 10).

The greater magnesium contents (0.49 ppm) were observed in plants grown at 25 °C (control) whereas among the heat stress levels highest magnesium contents (0.38 ppm) were observed at 40 °C followed by 45 °C (0.33 ppm) (Table 10). Data regarding magnesium contents revealed that at 40 °C highest reduction in magnesium contents was noted in Click-5769 (25.86 %), Ikra-2 (25.25 %), Okra-3 (24.90 %) and Ikra-3 (24.53 %). On the other hand, at 45 °C lowest reduction in magnesium contents was observed in Sabazpari (22.88 %), Green wonder (24.93 %), Punjab selection (25.59 %) and Kiran-51 (26.35 %) exhibited minimum reduction magnesium contents, as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 10). Average decrease in magnesium contents was observed higher in Click-5769 (32.52 %), Ikra-2 (31.78 %), Okra-3 (31.48 %) and Ikra-3 (31.01 %). Whereas, genotypes Sabazpari (19.72 %), Green wonder (20.97 %), Punjab selection (21.48 %) and Kiran-51 (22.15 %) were least affected by heat stress as they exhibited a minimum reduction in magnesium contents as compared to rest of okra genotypes (Table 10).

Based upon cluster analysis membership genotypes Kiran-51, Punjab selection, Ikra-1, Sarsabaz, Sanum, Pen beauty, Sabaz pari and Green wonder were categorized as thermo-tolerant whereas, Shehzadi, Lush green, OK-1307, Anarkali and OK-1305 were moderate-tolerant, while Ikra-3, MF-03, Okra-7100, Cick-576, Pusa sawani, Okra-3, and Ikra-2 were categorized as thermo-sensitive okra genotypes.

Discussion

A lot of investigations regarding heat stress have been done, but the literature on okra in this regard is scanty. Therefore, keeping in view the importance of okra as a globally grown and one of the most liked vegetables of Pakistan; present study was carried out to screen the available okra genotypes against heat stress tolerance. The finding of the recent study depicted that heat stress significantly affected the all tested okra genotypes regarding their germination and seedling growth, so these are considered as indicators of heat stress. Based upon these important tools, genotypes can be grouped into tolerant and sensitive once. Greater seed germination and seedling growth indicated the plants potential to resist the heat stress (Carpici *et al.*, 2009; Bitra and Gerats, 2013; Bange and Rose, 2018). Different research studies indicate that heat stress is a developmental stage specific process as one developmental stage may be drastically affected while others exhibit tolerance to heat stress (Johnson *et al.*, 1992; Hasanuzzaman *et al.*, 2013; Kaushal *et al.*, 2016; Sita *et al.*, 2017). Screening at seedling stage and germination test is a useful tool for screening under the stressed environment (Tlig *et al.*, 2008; Guan *et al.*, 2009; Chennupati *et al.*, 2011; Zou *et al.*, 2014). But the factors like seed age, climate conditions at harvesting and storage conditions may affect seed germination so it can be predicted that germination cannot be a reliable marker for screening under stress condition (Rubio-Casal *et al.*, 2003; Swapna *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, in the present study, it was ensured to eliminate the above said factors by taking seeds of uniform size, age and which were stored under similar conditions so the findings can be more real than apparent.

The seeds germination was reduced under heat stress (40 and 45 °C) compared with control (25 °C). The variation in germination can be due to excessive loss of moisture contents from seeds tissues which affected the minerals and organic reserves mobilization (Essemine *et al.*, 2010; Chennupati *et al.*, 2011; Mickky and Aldesuquy, 2017). The effects

of heat stress vary not only vary among genotypes but also within species. In this study, twenty different okra genotypes were for germination percentage under different heat stress conditions and were categorized into thermo-tolerant and thermo-sensitive on the basis of percent reduction in germination with respect to control. Genotypes like Sabazpari, Green wonder, Punjab selection and Pen beauty presented high germination percentage and were considered as heat tolerant. Whereas, Click-5769, Okra-3, Ikra-2, and Ikra-3 showed a greater reduction in germination percentage under heat stress and were regarded as heat sensitive okra genotypes.

The data regarding shoot length, root length, plant fresh weight and dry weight showed a strong negative correlation with heat stress and expressed a marked reduction in these growth characteristics of tested okra genotypes. Heat stress reduced the water potential of growth medium which leads to decrease in turgor potential and hence reduced/inhibited the cell elongation and division. As a result of this plant fresh biomass production gets reduced which not only reduced the shoot and root length but it also reduced the plant fresh and dry weight in all tested okra genotypes. So these plant parameters can be a useful tool for screening under heat stress conditions. Genotypes with less reduction in shoot length, root length, plant fresh weight and dry weight were placed in heat tolerant category while genotypes with a high reduction in these characteristics were grouped into heat sensitive category. These results also confirm the findings of Ashraf *et al.* (2008), Aguyoh *et al.* (2013), Aghamolki *et al.* (2014) and Anjum *et al.* (2014). Out of identified tolerant okra genotypes possessed a greater genetic potential for heat tolerance.

It is also reported that heat-stressed plants presented reduction in photosynthetic activity and stomatal conductance (Silva *et al.*, 2010; Gorai *et al.*, 2010; Wang *et al.*, 2016; Li *et al.*, 2017) therefore, it can also a reason for reduction in plant biomass as observed in this study. These results also confirm the findings of Keutgen and Pawelzik, (2009) and Hajlaoui *et al.* (2010). The thermo-tolerant genotypes successfully maintained higher plant biomass due to the low accumulation of toxic ions in their tissues while thermo-sensitive genotypes failed in this regard and presented low biomass production. Heat stress-induced a reduction in leaf area, photosynthetic activity, transpiration and stomatal conductance due to increase in ion toxicity, membrane damages, change in osmotic potential and production of reactive oxygen species. Similar observations are recorded for okra in the current study. The decrease in leaf area was greater in thermo-sensitive okra genotypes as compared to thermo-tolerant ones which resemble with previous findings of Abbruzzese *et al.* (2009), Jian-jun *et al.* (2010), Latef and Chaoxing (2011) and Hemantaranjan (2014). This reduction in leaf area can be responsible for the reduction in photosynthetic activity in tested okra genotypes due to a decrease in availability of photosynthetic area. Thermo-sensitive okra genotypes showed high percent decrease in leaf area, so they obviously presented low photosynthesis rate. Similar results have been reported by Nazar *et al.* (2011) at mungbean crop and find a significant reduction in various physiological attributes especially photosynthesis rate of stressed and nonstressed plants. However, the reduction in photosynthesis rate was observed lower in tolerant plants as compared to sensitive ones. Chlorophyll contents disturb stomatal conductance in plants (Matsumoto *et al.*, 2005; Hatfield *et al.*, 2011; Rejeb *et al.*, 2014; Li *et al.*, 2017) which influenced more in thermo-sensitive okra genotypes as compared to thermo-tolerant ones.

Different factors like salinity stress, water stress, disease and especially heat stress may lead to leaf necrosis and limit water movement in leaf. These factors cause the leaf tip burning; yellowing and dieback of leaf edges that reduce the production of new chlorophyll and leaves became yellow and scorched (Suzuki *et al.*, 2014; Bange and Rose, 2018). Similarly in this study under heat stress yellowing of leaves (necrosis) was noted in both thermo-tolerant and thermo-sensitive okra genotypes whereas, it was observed negligible in non stressed plants. Due to the necrosis reduction in leaf chlorophyll also reduced photosynthesis, stomatal conductance, transpiration rate and ultimate growth of the plant (Suarez *et al.*, 2008; Suzuki *et al.*, 2014; León-Sánchez *et al.*, 2016; Xia *et al.*, 2018; Bange and Rose, 2018). Photosynthesis and plant growth are the main processes affected by heat stress (Munns *et al.*, 2006; Pospisil and Prasad, 2014; Shirdelmoghanloo *et al.*, 2016; Awasthi *et al.*, 2017). In this study heat stress significantly reduced photosynthetic activity in both thermo-tolerant and thermo-sensitive okra genotypes but greater adverse effects of heat stress were observed in thermo-sensitive okra genotypes.

The generation of reactive oxygen species like hydroxyl radical, superoxide radical and hydrogen peroxide is the common phenomenon under stressed environment. These reactive oxygen species cause oxidative stress by oxidation of lipids, nucleic acids and proteins (McCord, 2000; Apel and Hirt, 2004; Finka *et al.*, 2012; Choudhury *et al.*, 2013). To overcome the oxidative damage under stressed conditions especially heats stress, plants develop an antioxidant defense system comprised of various antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase, peroxidase, peroxidase, etc. In this study stressed plants of tested okra genotypes showed an increased level of antioxidant enzymes (superoxide dismutase and peroxidase) as compared to non stressed plants. But the minimum activity of antioxidant enzymes was recorded in

thermo-sensitive okra genotypes as compared to thermo-tolerant ones. The increased level of antioxidant enzymes activity in thermo-tolerant okra genotypes demonstrated that these genotypes were well adapted to heat stress by eliminating reactive oxygen species. Whereas, thermo-sensitive okra genotypes failed to adjust themselves under heat stress because of less activity of antioxidant enzymes and resulted in the generation of highly reactive oxygen species which oxidized lipids and protein cell structure. These findings are in line with previous reports of Roychoudhury et al. (2011) who studied different rice varieties under abiotic stress environment and noticed significantly increased in antioxidant enzymes activities. Various other reports also support these findings (Seckin *et al.*, 2010; Nazar *et al.*, 2011; Tuteja and Gill, 2013; Martinez *et al.*, 2018).

Under stressed conditions, okra genotypes suffered from osmotic stress and followed the mechanism of osmotic adjustment by increasing the production of different organic osmolytes such as proline, glycinebetaine, sugars, amino acids, and proteins, etc. in their tissues. Due to this reason, thermo-tolerant okra genotypes presented high accumulation of organic solutes and have greater heat tolerance potential because these osmolytes maintain the turgor potential under heat stress, As a result of which plant regulated various metabolic processes in a better way compared to thermo-sensitive okra genotypes. Greater the production of these osmolytes ensures greater osmotic adjustment potential within the plant. The thermo-tolerant genotypes showed the high percentage increase in osmolytes as compared to thermo-sensitive ones. Maximum percentage increase of osmoprotectants in tolerant genotypes is the sign of efficient osmotic adjustment while minimum percentage increase of osmolytes in heat susceptible genotypes showed low osmotic adjustment potential under heat stress. A positive correlation was established between the number of osmoprotectants and thermo-tolerance. Similar kind of findings had been reported by Hajlaoui et al. (2010), Hassine and Lutts (2010), Li et al. (2010) and Kaushal et al. (2016).

Heat stress significantly influences nutrients status of the plant through the nutrient regulation process. It is well documented that heat stress suppresses the concentration of calcium and magnesium in plants (Akram *et al.*, 2010; Gilroy *et al.*, 2016; Fahad *et al.*, 2017) which are key ions for different physiological processes but under stress condition nutrients imbalance occur in plants. The current study indicates that tested okra genotypes exhibited a reduction in calcium and magnesium contents. However, genotypes Green wonder, Punjab selection, Sabazpari, Sarsabaz, and Kiran-51 presented less reduction in the concentration of these ions while Ikra-2, Okra-3, Click-5769, Pusasawani and Ikra-3 presented a greater reduction in this regard. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Khayat et al. (2010). The variation in the reduction of the concentration of calcium and magnesium concentration helped to figure out heat tolerant and heat sensitive okra genotypes under heat stress conditions (Hasanuzzaman *et al.*, 2013b; Mathiba *et al.*, 2018). The findings of this study may help to identify thermo-tolerant okra genotypes that can be grown under hot climate without affecting their yield and quality.

Summary

The present study was conducted to investigate the drastic effects of heat stress on growth and development of okra at the seedling stage. To achieve the goals of the study, twenty different okra genotypes were screened out for heat tolerance and categorized as thermo-sensitive, moderate-tolerant and thermo-tolerant on the basis of morphological, physiological, gasses exchange, enzymatic and ionic characteristics. This preliminary research can be used for exploring the new horizons in the breeding of okra and to utilize thermo-tolerant okra germplasm available in Pakistan for further research at reproductive and maturity stage to get its good yield for a longer period of time in hot climatic conditions.

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Table 1: Influence of high temperature stress on germination (%) and shoot length (cm) of okra genotypes

Genotypes	Temperature Treatments							
	Germination (%) ± S.E.				Shoot length ± S.E.			
	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean
Sabazpari	94.09± 1.02	80.01± 0.87	59.23± 0.68	77.78 ab	15.80 ± 0.30	12.93 ± 0.25	10.70 ± 0.20	13.15 f
Sarsabaz	92.54± 0.99	78.08± 0.83	65.09± 0.71	78.57 ab	21.43 ± 0.40	18.02 ± 0.34	15.35 ± 0.29	18.26 b
Pen beauty	90.85± 1.1	76.11± 0.85	63.00± 0.68	76.66 b	14.88 ± 0.28	11.61 ± 0.22	9.18 ± 0.17	11.89 gh
Green wonder	73.49± 0.90	65.78± 1.35	44.39± 0.91	61.22 gh	14.29 ± 0.27	11.27 ± 0.21	7.99 ± 0.14	11.18 hi
Punjab selection	74.74± 0.80	58.43± 0.63	45.09± 0.49	59.42 hi	13.72 ± 0.26	10.10 ± 0.19	7.54 ± 0.15	10.45 jk
Anarkali	84.10± 0.91	69.16± 0.75	56.19± 0.61	69.82 de	15.21 ± 0.29	12.33 ± 0.23	10.12 ± 0.19	12.55 fg
Shehzadi	89.98± 0.67	75.08± 0.81	70.90± 0.77	78.65 ab	17.89 ± 0.34	14.84 ± 0.28	12.45 ± 0.23	15.06 d
Ikra-3	74.01± 0.80	57.62± 0.69	51.20± 0.56	60.94 gh	13.72 ± 0.26	10.02 ± 0.19	7.41 ± 0.14	10.38 k
Ikra-1	67.86± 0.74	51.67± 0.56	38.82± 0.43	52.78 k	12.80 ± 0.24	9.16 ± 0.17	6.64 ± 0.16	9.53 l
Kiran-51	81.54± 0.95	65.96± 0.70	52.70± 0.57	66.73 f	14.31 ± 0.27	11.01 ± 0.21	8.58 ± 0.12	11.30 hi
Okra-7100	76.05± 0.88	60.18± 0.62	47.02± 0.60	61.08 gh	14.29 ± 0.30	10.79 ± 0.20	8.28 ± 0.16	11.12 ij
Sanum	87.69± 0.82	72.82± 0.79	55.38± 0.51	71.97 cd	16.96 ± 0.32	13.96 ± 0.26	11.63 ± 0.22	14.19 e
Lush green	81.48± 0.78	65.64± 0.71	60.09± 0.65	69.07 e	15.21 ± 0.29	11.91 ± 0.22	9.92 ± 0.19	12.35 g
Ikra-2	75.23± 0.92	59.32± 0.64	46.18± 0.73	60.24 gh	13.08 ± 0.23	9.44 ± 0.18	6.90 ± 0.13	9.81 kl
OK-1305	85.13± 0.71	70.47± 0.89	64.67± 0.46	73.42 c	20.24 ± 0.38	16.88 ± 0.32	14.25 ± 0.27	17.12 c
OK-1307	72.14± 0.96	55.60± 0.60	42.86± 0.63	56.87 j	12.00 ± 0.23	8.41 ± 0.16	5.90 ± 0.11	8.77 m
Pusasawani	84.39± 1.01	79.36± 0.86	57.96± 0.52	73.90 c	22.35 ± 0.42	18.87 ± 0.35	16.12 ± 0.30	19.11 a
MF-03	70.42± 0.67	53.99± 0.59	48.41± 0.52	57.61 ij	12.53 ± 0.24	8.90 ± 0.17	6.42 ± 0.12	9.28 lm
Okra-3	77.17±0.84	61.33± 0.67	48.13± 0.67	62.21 g	15.21 ± 0.29	12.14 ± 0.23	9.76 ± 0.28	12.37 g
Click-5769	93.41± 1.04	79.30± 0.86	66.53± 0.72	79.75 a	21.16 ± 0.41	17.75 ± 0.33	15.05 ± 0.18	17.99 b
Mean	81.32 a	66.80 b	54.19 c	67.43	15.85 a	12.51 b	10.01 c	12.79

Table 2: Influence of high temperature stress on root length (cm) and fresh plant weight (g) of okra genotypes

Genotypes	Temperature Treatments							
	Root length \pm S.E.				Plant fresh weight \pm S.E.			
	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean
Sabazpari	8.24 \pm 0.14	6.83 \pm 0.16	5.72 \pm 0.10	6.93 ef	59.24 \pm 0.83	45.07 \pm 0.63	34.29 \pm 0.48	46.20 ef
Sarsabaz	11.35 \pm 0.19	9.65 \pm 0.11	8.44 \pm 0.14	9.81 a	77.39 \pm 1.08	61.71 \pm 0.86	49.39 \pm 0.69	62.83 b
Pen beauty	7.40 \pm 0.11	5.69 \pm 0.09	4.42 \pm 0.07	5.84 ij	52.49 \pm 0.73	38.74 \pm 0.54	28.59 \pm 0.40	39.94 hij
Green wonder	6.74 \pm 0.12	4.99 \pm 0.08	3.75 \pm 0.06	5.16 lm	52.31 \pm 0.73	38.16 \pm 0.53	27.84 \pm 0.39	39.44 ijk
Punjab selection	6.98 \pm 0.18	5.25 \pm 0.11	3.98 \pm 0.09	5.40 kl	50.37 \pm 0.70	35.64 \pm 0.50	25.22 \pm 0.35	37.08 lm
Anarkali	8.05 \pm 0.12	6.61 \pm 0.09	5.49 \pm 0.07	6.72 fg	60.61 \pm 0.85	46.57 \pm 0.65	35.78 \pm 0.50	47.65 e
Shehzadi	10.86 \pm 0.13	9.17 \pm 0.15	7.89 \pm 0.13	9.31 b	73.77 \pm 1.03	57.56 \pm 0.80	44.92 \pm 0.63	58.75 c
Ikra-3	7.28 \pm 0.15	5.53 \pm 0.09	4.25 \pm 0.07	5.69 jk	50.96 \pm 0.71	36.24 \pm 0.51	25.78 \pm 0.36	37.66 kl
Ikra-1	6.36 \pm 0.12	4.62 \pm 0.08	3.38 \pm 0.06	4.79 no	47.93 \pm 0.67	33.83 \pm 0.47	23.87 \pm 0.33	35.21 mn
Kiran-51	7.46 \pm 0.11	5.77 \pm 0.10	4.54 \pm 0.08	5.92 ij	53.35 \pm 0.74	39.69 \pm 0.55	29.52 \pm 0.41	40.85 hi
Okra-7100	7.64 \pm 0.12	5.96 \pm 0.12	4.77 \pm 0.08	6.13 hi	53.86 \pm 0.75	40.24 \pm 0.56	30.06 \pm 0.42	41.39 h
Sanum	8.36 \pm 0.13	6.95 \pm 0.10	5.86 \pm 0.10	7.06 e	63.52 \pm 0.89	48.99 \pm 0.68	37.78 \pm 0.53	50.10 d
Lush green	7.88 \pm 0.14	6.26 \pm 0.13	5.03 \pm 0.08	6.39 gh	56.02 \pm 0.78	42.20 \pm 0.59	31.78 \pm 0.44	43.33 g
Ikra-2	6.57 \pm 0.13	4.80 \pm 0.08	3.56 \pm 0.06	4.98 mn	51.90 \pm 0.72	36.93 \pm 0.52	26.28 \pm 0.37	38.37 jkl
OK-1305	10.21 \pm 0.17	8.58 \pm 0.14	7.33 \pm 0.12	8.71 c	64.46 \pm 0.90	50.08 \pm 0.70	38.91 \pm 0.54	51.15 d
OK-1307	6.28 \pm 0.11	4.50 \pm 0.08	3.29 \pm 0.05	4.69 no	44.28 \pm 0.62	30.69 \pm 0.43	21.28 \pm 0.30	32.08 o
Pusasawani	11.12 \pm 0.19	9.42 \pm 0.16	8.16 \pm 0.17	9.57 ab	80.30 \pm 1.12	64.26 \pm 0.90	52.44 \pm 0.73	65.67 a
MF-03	6.25 \pm 0.07	4.45 \pm 0.07	3.22 \pm 0.05	4.64 o	47.28 \pm 0.66	33.10 \pm 0.46	23.18 \pm 0.32	34.52 n
Okra-3	7.95 \pm 0.11	6.42 \pm 0.13	5.22 \pm 0.09	6.53 g	57.10 \pm 0.80	43.31 \pm 0.60	32.86 \pm 0.46	44.42 fg
Click-5769	9.04 \pm 0.13	7.56 \pm 0.11	6.41 \pm 0.11	7.67 d	74.97 \pm 1.05	59.59 \pm 0.83	47.37 \pm 0.66	60.64 c
Mean	8.10 a	6.45 b	5.23 c	6.60	58.61 a	44.13 ab	33.36 b	45.37

Table 3: Influence of high temperature stress on plant dry weight (g) and number of leaves per plant of okra genotypes

Genotypes	Temperature Treatments							
	Plant dry weight \pm S.E.				A number of leaves per plant \pm S.E.			
	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean
Sabazpari	8.04 \pm 0.11	6.23 \pm 0.09	5.45 \pm 0.10	6.57 e	6.82 \pm 0.12	5.58 \pm 0.10	4.62 \pm 0.07	5.67 c
Sarsabaz	10.48 \pm 0.15	8.77 \pm 0.12	7.96 \pm 0.14	9.07 b	6.05 \pm 0.10	4.89 \pm 0.08	4.01 \pm 0.09	4.98 e
Pen beauty	6.78 \pm 0.09	5.09 \pm 0.07	4.28 \pm 0.09	5.38 hi	4.80 \pm 0.08	3.73 \pm 0.06	2.95 \pm 0.05	3.82 gh
Green wonder	6.69 \pm 0.09	4.95 \pm 0.07	4.33 \pm 0.10	5.32 hi	4.13 \pm 0.07	3.06 \pm 0.09	2.34 \pm 0.10	3.18 kl
Punjab selection	6.36 \pm 0.09	4.59 \pm 0.06	3.74 \pm 0.08	4.90 jk	4.42 \pm 0.08	3.35 \pm 0.06	2.62 \pm 0.05	3.46 ij
Anarkali	8.08 \pm 0.11	6.44 \pm 0.09	5.72 \pm 0.07	6.74 e	5.28 \pm 0.09	4.16 \pm 0.07	3.38 \pm 0.10	4.27 f
Shehzadi	9.30 \pm 0.13	7.63 \pm 0.11	6.86 \pm 0.05	7.93 d	6.53 \pm 0.11	5.31 \pm 0.09	4.38 \pm 0.07	5.40 d
Ikra-3	6.47 \pm 0.09	4.70 \pm 0.07	3.85 \pm 0.06	5.00 j	4.22 \pm 0.07	3.14 \pm 0.08	2.42 \pm 0.06	3.26 jkl
Ikra-1	6.08 \pm 0.08	4.36 \pm 0.06	3.55 \pm 0.11	4.67 kl	3.74 \pm 0.10	2.69 \pm 0.09	2.02 \pm 0.07	2.82 m
Kiran-51	6.80 \pm 0.09	5.48 \pm 0.08	4.31 \pm 0.06	5.53 gh	4.99 \pm 0.06	3.91 \pm 0.05	3.12 \pm 0.03	4.01 g
Okra-7100	6.85 \pm 0.10	5.20 \pm 0.07	4.42 \pm 0.09	5.49 gh	4.32 \pm 0.09	3.23 \pm 0.11	2.49 \pm 0.06	3.35 jk
Sanum	8.16 \pm 0.11	6.53 \pm 0.09	5.81 \pm 0.07	6.83 e	5.86 \pm 0.07	4.69 \pm 0.05	3.83 \pm 0.07	4.79 e
Lush green	7.07 \pm 0.10	5.37 \pm 0.07	4.59 \pm 0.06	5.68 g	6.91 \pm 0.10	5.66 \pm 0.07	4.72 \pm 0.08	5.76 c
Ikra-2	6.61 \pm 0.09	4.84 \pm 0.07	3.98 \pm 0.10	5.14 ij	4.32 \pm 0.12	3.26 \pm 0.09	2.53 \pm 0.04	3.37 jk
OK-1305	8.09 \pm 0.11	6.53 \pm 0.09	5.83 \pm 0.05	6.82 e	4.90 \pm 0.07	3.83 \pm 0.06	3.04 \pm 0.05	3.93 g
OK-1307	5.82 \pm 0.08	4.14 \pm 0.06	3.34 \pm 0.10	4.44 l	4.04 \pm 0.08	2.93 \pm 0.07	2.22 \pm 0.04	3.06 l
Pusasawani	11.54 \pm 0.16	9.58 \pm 0.13	8.72 \pm 0.15	9.95 a	7.49 \pm 0.13	6.19 \pm 0.10	5.20 \pm 0.09	6.29 a
MF-03	5.95 \pm 0.08	4.25 \pm 0.06	3.45 \pm 0.05	4.55 l	4.13 \pm 0.09	3.01 \pm 0.07	2.32 \pm 0.04	3.15 kl
Okra-3	7.58 \pm 0.11	5.84 \pm 0.08	5.03 \pm 0.09	6.15 f	4.62 \pm 0.08	3.56 \pm 0.06	2.79 \pm 0.05	3.66 hi
Click-5769	9.59 \pm 0.13	7.91 \pm 0.11	7.12 \pm 0.10	8.21 c	7.21 \pm 0.12	5.94 \pm 0.09	4.99 \pm 0.10	6.05 b
Mean	7.62 a	5.92 b	5.12 c	6.22	5.24 a	4.11 b	3.30 c	4.21

Table 4: Influence of high temperature stress on leaf area (cm²) and transpiration rate (mmol H₂O m⁻² S⁻¹) of okra genotypes

Genotypes	Temperature Treatments							
	Leaf area ± S.E.				Transpiration rate ± S.E.			
	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean
Sabazpari	16.43 ± 0.19	13.66 ± 0.12	12.16 ± 0.150	14.08 cd	2.01 ± 0.029	1.61 ± 0.033	1.48 ± 0.024	1.70 cd
Sarsabaz	17.34 ± 0.20	14.57 ± 0.17	13.12 ± 0.14	15.01 b	2.02 ± 0.032	1.59 ± 0.028	1.42 ± 0.037	1.67 e
Pen beauty	15.23 ± 0.16	12.25 ± 0.15	10.35 ± 0.12	12.61 fg	1.99 ± 0.028	1.50 ± 0.030	1.37 ± 0.036	1.62 g
Green wonder	12.44 ± 0.15	9.60 ± 0.13	7.95 ± 0.09	9.99 j	1.90 ± 0.040	1.37 ± 0.025	1.29 ± 0.030	1.52 i
Punjab selection	13.99 ± 0.16	10.88 ± 0.14	9.09 ± 0.13	11.32 h	1.83 ± 0.031	1.27 ± 0.026	1.20 ± 0.021	1.43 l
Anarkali	15.72 ± 0.19	12.92 ± 0.16	11.17 ± 0.15	13.27 e	2.03 ± 0.039	1.64 ± 0.023	1.44 ± 0.031	1.71 c
Shehzadi	16.18 ± 0.19	13.37 ± 0.12	11.72 ± 0.14	13.76 d	1.99 ± 0.039	1.54 ± 0.024	1.40 ± 0.032	1.64 f
Ikra-3	13.28 ± 0.16	10.30 ± 0.11	8.56 ± 0.13	10.71 i	1.88 ± 0.037	1.34 ± 0.028	1.26 ± 0.022	1.49 j
Ikra-1	11.24 ± 0.13	8.48 ± 0.14	6.95 ± 0.10	8.89 l	1.81 ± 0.027	1.23 ± 0.038	1.17 ± 0.033	1.40 m
Kiran-51	14.86 ± 0.18	11.91 ± 0.14	10.03 ± 0.12	12.27 g	1.94 ± 0.025	1.42 ± 0.031	1.34 ± 0.038	1.57 h
Okra-7100	14.80 ± 0.19	11.82 ± 0.13	9.93 ± 0.10	12.18 g	1.91 ± 0.030	1.44 ± 0.026	1.34 ± 0.034	1.56 h
Sanum	16.18 ± 0.18	13.44 ± 0.15	11.84 ± 0.16	13.82 d	2.00 ± 0.027	1.60 ± 0.036	1.43 ± 0.031	1.67 e
Lush green	15.50 ± 0.18	12.52 ± 0.16	10.63 ± 0.13	12.88 ef	1.98 ± 0.036	1.43 ± 0.028	1.54 ± 0.021	1.65 f
Ikra-2	14.22 ± 0.17	11.23 ± 0.13	9.40 ± 0.15	11.62 h	1.85 ± 0.028	1.37 ± 0.024	1.23 ± 0.033	1.48 jk
OK-1305	16.57 ± 0.20	13.87 ± 0.16	12.45 ± 0.09	14.30 c	2.02 ± 0.024	1.59 ± 0.035	1.46 ± 0.030	1.69 de
OK-1307	11.90 ± 0.15	9.11 ± 0.11	7.48 ± 0.17	9.50 k	1.86 ± 0.032	1.30 ± 0.026	1.24 ± 0.022	1.47 k
Pusasawani	17.94 ± 0.21	15.27 ± 0.18	14.06 ± 0.14	15.76 a	2.07 ± 0.025	1.70 ± 0.030	1.52 ± 0.037	1.76 a
MF-03	12.13 ± 0.17	9.34 ± 0.11	7.70 ± 0.09	9.72 jk	1.87 ± 0.040	1.33 ± 0.033	1.24 ± 0.025	1.48 j
Okra-3	15.70 ± 0.16	12.89 ± 0.13	10.99 ± 0.13	13.19 e	1.90 ± 0.028	1.40 ± 0.041	1.27 ± 0.034	1.52 i
Click-5769	17.34 ± 0.17	14.65 ± 0.14	13.25 ± 0.16	15.08 b	2.04 ± 0.032	1.63 ± 0.040	1.53 ± 0.021	1.73 b
Mean	14.95 a	12.10 b	10.44 c	12.50	1.94 a	1.47 b	1.36 c	1.59

Table 5: Influence of high temperature stress on photosynthesis rate ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$) and stomatal conductance ($\text{mmol m}^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$) of okra genotypes

Genotypes	Temperature Treatments							
	Photosynthesis rate \pm S.E.				Stomatal conductance \pm S.E.			
	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean
Sabazpari	20.55 \pm 0.37	16.62 \pm 0.28	13.47 \pm 0.41	16.88 fg	65.37 \pm 0.66	54.06 \pm 0.39	45.90 \pm 0.43	55.11 cde
Sarsabaz	29.89 \pm 0.55	25.08 \pm 0.30	21.14 \pm 0.38	25.37 b	68.24 \pm 0.37	56.97 \pm 0.23	48.88 \pm 0.52	58.03 bc
Pen beauty	18.60 \pm 0.32	14.44 \pm 0.44	11.50 \pm 0.47	14.85 hi	60.28 \pm 0.30	47.56 \pm 0.29	38.06 \pm 0.20	48.63 ghij
Green wonder	17.45 \pm 0.30	13.44 \pm 0.51	11.57 \pm 0.31	14.15 ij	58.11 \pm 0.66	44.25 \pm 0.38	32.81 \pm 0.26	45.05 klm
Punjab selection	17.10 \pm 0.38	12.85 \pm 0.43	9.91 \pm 0.27	13.29 jkl	59.27 \pm 0.55	45.79 \pm 0.21	34.65 \pm 0.35	46.57 jklm
Anarkali	21.68 \pm 0.57	17.64 \pm 0.36	14.37 \pm 0.40	17.90 f	61.38 \pm 0.47	49.42 \pm 0.28	41.07 \pm 0.51	50.63 fgh
Shehzadi	25.76 \pm 0.48	21.31 \pm 0.31	17.71 \pm 0.44	21.60 d	62.66 \pm 0.41	50.56 \pm 0.37	42.36 \pm 0.60	51.86 efg
Ikra-3	17.29 \pm 0.29	13.19 \pm 0.38	10.32 \pm 0.21	13.60 jk	58.57 \pm 0.32	44.89 \pm 0.27	33.67 \pm 0.71	45.71 jklm
Ikra-1	16.81 \pm 0.41	12.59 \pm 0.56	9.65 \pm 0.40	13.01 jkl	57.43 \pm 0.25	43.12 \pm 0.36	30.66 \pm 0.37	43.74 m
Kiran-51	18.69 \pm 0.33	14.77 \pm 0.38	11.68 \pm 0.47	15.04 hi	59.86 \pm 0.39	46.98 \pm 0.42	37.07 \pm 0.28	47.97 hijk
Okra-7100	18.84 \pm 0.42	16.23 \pm 0.55	12.20 \pm 0.28	15.76 gh	59.78 \pm 0.30	46.66 \pm 0.52	36.28 \pm 0.21	47.57 hijkl
Sanum	23.03 \pm 0.38	18.84 \pm 0.29	15.41 \pm 0.24	19.09 e	63.34 \pm 0.26	52.00 \pm 0.41	43.84 \pm 0.28	53.06 def
Lush green	19.03 \pm 0.52	15.16 \pm 0.26	12.22 \pm 0.47	15.47 h	60.45 \pm 0.38	47.94 \pm 0.34	37.55 \pm 0.34	48.65 ghij
Ikra-2	17.33 \pm 0.71	13.22 \pm 0.44	10.41 \pm 0.31	13.65 jk	59.62 \pm 0.28	46.48 \pm 0.42	35.74 \pm 0.43	47.28 ijkl
OK-1305	23.78 \pm 0.33	19.54 \pm 0.27	16.05 \pm 0.33	19.79 e	66.22 \pm 0.22	54.99 \pm 0.33	46.97 \pm 0.62	56.06 cd
OK-1307	16.08 \pm 0.27	11.91 \pm 0.38	9.06 \pm 0.29	12.35 l	57.69 \pm 0.32	43.49 \pm 0.27	31.78 \pm 0.52	44.32 lm
Pusasawani	32.23 \pm 0.43	27.07 \pm 0.50	22.94 \pm 0.39	27.41 a	72.60 \pm 0.39	61.03 \pm 0.23	52.75 \pm 0.44	62.13 a
MF-03	16.77 \pm 0.62	12.47 \pm 0.35	9.53 \pm 0.31	12.92 kl	57.92 \pm 0.48	43.87 \pm 0.29	32.26 \pm 0.60	44.69 lm
Okra-3	19.37 \pm 0.21	15.51 \pm 0.38	12.52 \pm 0.28	15.80 gh	61.18 \pm 0.57	49.00 \pm 0.38	39.88 \pm 0.33	50.02 fghi
Click-5769	28.22 \pm 0.40	23.47 \pm 0.47	19.76 \pm 0.43	23.82 c	70.64 \pm 0.47	59.14 \pm 0.35	50.97 \pm 0.29	60.25 ab
Mean	20.93 a	16.77 b	13.57 c	17.09	62.03 a	49.41 b	39.66 c	50.37

Table 6: Influence of high temperature stress on leaf and root proline contents ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ FW) of okra genotypes

Genotypes	Temperature Treatments							
	Leaf proline contents \pm S.E.				Root proline contents \pm S.E.			
	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean
Sabazpari	1.54 \pm 0.017	1.78 \pm 0.020	1.89 \pm 0.021	174 bc	1.09 \pm 0.019	1.25 \pm 0.023	1.34 \pm 0.015	1.23 cd
Sarsabaz	1.57 \pm 0.015	1.82 \pm 0.018	1.93 \pm 0.019	1.78 b	1.10 \pm 0.018	1.27 \pm 0.021	1.37 \pm 0.017	1.25 bc
Pen beauty	1.41 \pm 0.017	1.60 \pm 0.020	1.69 \pm 0.021	1.57 f	1.02 \pm 0.020	1.15 \pm 0.011	1.23 \pm 0.024	1.13 afgh
Green wonder	1.24 \pm 0.014	1.39 \pm 0.015	1.47 \pm 0.018	1.36 j	0.96 \pm 0.017	1.07 \pm 0.019	1.13 \pm 0.022	1.05 ij
Punjab selection	1.35 \pm 0.015	1.52 \pm 0.017	1.61 \pm 0.016	1.49 gh	0.98 \pm 0.017	1.10 \pm 0.015	1.16 \pm 0.021	1.08 hi
Anarkali	1.47 \pm 0.016	1.68 \pm 0.018	1.78 \pm 0.018	1.64 de	1.02 \pm 0.018	1.17 \pm 0.016	1.25 \pm 0.017	1.15 efg
Shehzadi	1.51 \pm 0.017	1.74 \pm 0.019	1.85 \pm 0.020	1.70 cd	1.08 \pm 0.019	1.24 \pm 0.020	1.33 \pm 0.025	1.22 cd
Ikra-3	1.29 \pm 0.014	1.45 \pm 0.016	1.53 \pm 0.020	1.42 i	0.96 \pm 0.017	1.08 \pm 0.016	1.14 \pm 0.022	1.06 ij
Ikra-1	1.15 \pm 0.016	1.26 \pm 0.014	1.34 \pm 0.017	1.25 k	0.81 \pm 0.019	0.90 \pm 0.013	0.94 \pm 0.026	0.88 l
Kiran-51	1.47 \pm 0.013	1.67 \pm 0.017	1.77 \pm 0.015	1.64 e	1.02 \pm 0.014	1.16 \pm 0.016	1.24 \pm 0.023	1.14 efgh
Okra-7100	1.39 \pm 0.016	1.57 \pm 0.018	1.67 \pm 0.019	1.54 fg	1.01 \pm 0.018	1.15 \pm 0.012	1.22 \pm 0.021	1.13 fgh
Sanum	1.49 \pm 0.016	1.72 \pm 0.019	1.82 \pm 0.018	1.68 cde	1.07 \pm 0.019	1.22 \pm 0.022	1.31 \pm 0.023	1.20 cde
Lush green	1.37 \pm 0.040	1.56 \pm 0.045	1.65 \pm 0.020	1.52 fg	1.02 \pm 0.019	1.16 \pm 0.021	1.24 \pm 0.018	1.14 efgh
Ikra-2	1.32 \pm 0.029	1.49 \pm 0.032	1.58 \pm 0.048	1.46 hi	0.99 \pm 0.018	1.11 \pm 0.020	1.18 \pm 0.027	1.09 ghi
OK-1305	1.49 \pm 0.016	1.70 \pm 0.019	1.80 \pm 0.034	1.66 de	1.04 \pm 0.016	1.19 \pm 0.021	1.28 \pm 0.019	1.17 def
OK-1307	1.22 \pm 0.013	1.35 \pm 0.015	1.43 \pm 0.020	1.34 j	0.92 \pm 0.021	1.03 \pm 0.018	1.08 \pm 0.022	1.01 jk
Pusasawani	1.63 \pm 0.018	1.92 \pm 0.021	2.05 \pm 0.016	1.87 a	1.18 \pm 0.016	1.37 \pm 0.024	1.50 \pm 0.026	1.35 a
MF-03	1.20 \pm 0.013	1.32 \pm 0.015	1.40 \pm 0.023	1.31 jk	0.90 \pm 0.018	1.00 \pm 0.018	1.05 \pm 0.015	0.99 k
Okra-3	1.40 \pm 0.015	1.58 \pm 0.017	1.68 \pm 0.018	1.55 f	1.02 \pm 0.020	1.15 \pm 0.021	1.22 \pm 0.024	1.13 fgh
Click-5769	1.63 \pm 0.018	1.90 \pm 0.021	2.02 \pm 0.022	1.85 a	1.15 \pm 0.019	1.32 \pm 0.024	1.44 \pm 0.020	1.30 ab
Mean	1.41 c	1.60 b	1.70 a	1.57	1.02 c	1.16 b	1.23 a	1.13

Table 7: Influence of high temperature stress on leaf and root glycinebetaine contents ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ FW) of okra genotypes

Genotypes	Temperature Treatments							
	Leaf glycinebetaine contents \pm S.E.				Root glycinebetaine contents \pm S.E.			
	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean
Sabazpari	1.75 \pm 0.046	2.06 \pm 0.044	2.21 \pm 0.053	2.01 cde	1.07 \pm 0.031	1.21 \pm 0.027	1.28 \pm 0.033	1.18 bc
Sarsabaz	1.92 \pm 0.040	2.29 \pm 0.055	2.48 \pm 0.059	2.23 a	1.12 \pm 0.022	1.28 \pm 0.031	1.36 \pm 0.035	1.25 ab
Pen beauty	1.66 \pm 0.049	1.91 \pm 0.046	2.02 \pm 0.049	1.86 fgh	0.97 \pm 0.026	1.09 \pm 0.028	1.15 \pm 0.030	1.07 efgh
Green wonder	1.63 \pm 0.039	1.87 \pm 0.045	1.98 \pm 0.047	1.83 gh	0.86 \pm 0.033	0.95 \pm 0.025	1.01 \pm 0.026	0.94 ijk
Punjab selection	1.52 \pm 0.036	1.72 \pm 0.041	1.81 \pm 0.038	1.68 ijk	0.93 \pm 0.027	1.03 \pm 0.022	1.09 \pm 0.028	1.02 ghi
Anarkali	1.78 \pm 0.043	2.11 \pm 0.053	2.25 \pm 0.046	2.05 bcd	1.03 \pm 0.024	1.17 \pm 0.024	1.23 \pm 0.032	1.14 cde
Shehzadi	1.81 \pm 0.043	2.15 \pm 0.046	2.31 \pm 0.051	2.09 bc	1.06 \pm 0.022	1.20 \pm 0.027	1.27 \pm 0.033	1.17 bcd
Ikra-3	1.59 \pm 0.048	1.82 \pm 0.039	1.92 \pm 0.044	1.78 hij	0.91 \pm 0.033	1.02 \pm 0.027	1.08 \pm 0.024	1.00 hij
Ikra-1	1.51 \pm 0.038	1.71 \pm 0.042	1.79 \pm 0.056	1.67 ijk	0.80 \pm 0.021	0.88 \pm 0.024	0.93 \pm 0.028	0.87 k
Kiran-51	1.66 \pm 0.040	1.92 \pm 0.047	2.03 \pm 0.033	1.87 fgh	0.96 \pm 0.025	1.08 \pm 0.023	1.14 \pm 0.029	1.06 efgh
Okra-7100	1.66 \pm 0.043	1.94 \pm 0.036	2.06 \pm 0.058	1.89 efgh	0.96 \pm 0.022	1.08 \pm 0.029	1.14 \pm 0.033	1.06 fgh
Sanum	1.79 \pm 0.043	2.12 \pm 0.044	2.27 \pm 0.039	2.06 bcd	1.06 \pm 0.031	1.20 \pm 0.027	1.28 \pm 0.029	1.18 bcd
Lush green	1.70 \pm 0.036	1.98 \pm 0.046	2.11 \pm 0.057	1.93 defg	0.99 \pm 0.034	1.12 \pm 0.031	1.18 \pm 0.033	1.10 defg
Ikra-2	1.61 \pm 0.039	1.84 \pm 0.051	1.95 \pm 0.047	1.80 ghi	0.94 \pm 0.028	1.05 \pm 0.029	1.11 \pm 0.025	1.03 gh
OK-1305	1.79 \pm 0.040	2.12 \pm 0.055	2.28 \pm 0.049	2.07 bc	1.08 \pm 0.022	1.23 \pm 0.031	1.30 \pm 0.037	1.20 bc
OK-1307	1.44 \pm 0.043	1.64 \pm 0.037	1.72 \pm 0.055	1.60 k	0.84 \pm 0.037	0.92 \pm 0.032	0.98 \pm 0.026	0.91 k
Pusasawani	1.94 \pm 0.041	2.32 \pm 0.046	2.53 \pm 0.060	2.26 a	1.18 \pm 0.031	1.35 \pm 0.039	1.44 \pm 0.031	1.32 a
MF-03	1.49 \pm 0.045	1.69 \pm 0.040	1.78 \pm 0.043	1.66 jk	0.85 \pm 0.025	0.94 \pm 0.030	1.00 \pm 0.036	0.93 jk
Okra-3	1.73 \pm 0.038	2.02 \pm 0.053	2.16 \pm 0.049	1.97 cdef	1.02 \pm 0.026	1.14 \pm 0.029	1.21 \pm 0.033	1.12 cdef
Click-5769	1.87 \pm 0.042	2.23 \pm 0.049	2.41 \pm 0.038	2.17 ab	1.16 \pm 0.030	1.32 \pm 0.034	1.41 \pm 0.027	1.30 a
Mean	1.69 c	1.97 b	2.10 a	1.92	0.99 c	1.11 b	1.18 a	1.09

Table 8: Influence of high temperature stress on leaf and root SOD contents (units mg⁻¹ protein) of okra genotypes

Genotypes	Temperature Treatments							
	Leaf SOD contents ± S.E.				Root SOD ± S.E.			
	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean
Sabazpari	7.58± 0.149	8.56± 0.143	9.36± 0.158	8.50 bc	4.00± 0.154	4.55± 0.143	4.98± 0.161	4.51 bc
Sarsabaz	7.67± 0.168	8.74± 0.129	9.61± 0.141	8.67 b	4.10± 0.124	4.68± 0.107	5.14± 0.127	4.64 b
Pen beauty	7.01± 0.184	7.75± 0.140	8.25± 0.127	7.67 def	3.66± 0.141	4.06± 0.132	4.35± 0.146	4.03 def
Green wonder	6.52± 0.151	7.09± 0.148	7.51± 0.138	7.04 h	3.45± 0.127	3.78± 0.128	4.03± 0.126	3.75 fg
Punjab selection	6.63± 0.172	7.26± 0.122	7.70± 0.146	7.19 gh	3.61± 0.133	3.97± 0.123	4.23± 0.134	3.93 defg
Anarkali	7.13± 0.138	7.96± 0.129	8.57± 0.206	7.89 def	3.76± 0.145	4.22± 0.142	4.56± 0.133	4.18 cde
Shehzadi	7.25± 0.152	8.15± 0.113	8.88± 0.186	8.09 cd	3.96± 0.159	4.49± 0.112	4.91± 0.120	4.45 bc
Ikra-3	6.54± 0.189	7.13± 0.140	7.55± 0.162	7.07 h	3.51± 0.126	3.85± 0.115	4.11± 0.112	3.82 efg
Ikra-1	5.74± 0.162	6.21± 0.155	6.55± 0.127	6.17 i	3.12± 0.135	3.38± 0.117	3.61± 0.103	3.37 h
Kiran-51	7.11± 0.148	7.90± 0.159	8.46± 0.138	7.82 def	3.74± 0.125	4.18± 0.113	4.50± 0.137	4.14 cde
Okra-7100	6.93± 0.139	7.63± 0.173	8.11± 0.145	7.56 fg	3.64± 0.117	4.02± 0.125	4.29± 0.158	3.98 def
Sanum	7.21± 0.128	8.10± 0.159	8.78± 0.137	8.03 de	3.79± 0.107	4.28± 0.133	4.66± 0.174	4.24 cd
Lush green	6.25± 0.130	6.93± 0.142	7.41± 0.151	6.86 h	3.70± 0.122	4.13± 0.139	4.60± 0.107	4.15 cde
Ikra-2	6.90± 0.140	7.58± 0.123	8.13± 0.160	7.54 fg	3.61± 0.123	3.99± 0.129	4.25± 0.116	3.95 defg
OK-1305	7.15± 0.143	8.02± 0.146	8.67± 0.154	7.95 def	3.77± 0.131	4.24± 0.116	4.59± 0.124	4.20 cd
OK-1307	6.46± 0.151	7.02± 0.136	7.42± 0.176	6.97 h	3.44± 0.122	3.76± 0.112	4.01± 0.142	3.74 fgh
Pusasawani	8.24± 0.168	9.47± 0.149	10.46± 0.194	9.39 a	4.41± 0.139	5.09± 0.105	5.61± 0.131	5.04 a
MF-03	6.45± 0.157	7.00± 0.137	7.40± 0.131	6.95 h	3.33± 0.141	3.63± 0.097	3.87± 0.117	3.61 gh
Okra-3	6.95± 0.175	7.67± a0.160	8.15± 0.168	7.59 efg	3.66± 0.152	4.06± 0.109	4.34± 0.111	4.02 def
Click-5769	7.83± 0.160	8.96± 0.170	9.88± 0.138	8.89 b	4.11± 0.127	4.71± 0.119	5.19± 0.115	4.67 ab
Mean	6.98 c	7.76 b	8.34 a	7.69	3.72 c	4.15 b	4.49 a	4.12

Table 9: Influence of high temperature stress on Leaf and root POD contents (units mg⁻¹ protein) of okra genotypes

Genotypes	Temperature Treatments							
	Leaf POD ± S.E.				Root POD ± S.E.			
	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean
Sabazpari	0.123± 0.003	0.141± 0.003	0.152± 0.002	0.139 cd	0.065± 0.002	0.075± 0.001	0.081± 0.001	0.074 cd
Sarsabaz	0.128± 0.003	0.147± 0.004	0.159± 0.004	0.145 bc	0.067± 0.002	0.078± 0.003	0.085± 0.001	0.077 c
Pen beauty	0.105± 0.004	0.119± 0.002	0.127± 0.003	0.117 hij	0.058± 0.001	0.066± 0.002	0.070± 0.002	0.064 gh
Green wonder	0.093± 0.002	0.105± 0.002	0.110± 0.003	0.103 klm	0.056± 0.002	0.063± 0.002	0.066± 0.001	0.062 hi
Punjab selection	0.096± 0.003	0.107± 0.004	0.114± 0.003	0.106 kl	0.050± 0.002	0.057± 0.001	0.060± 0.001	0.056 jk
Anarkali	0.113± 0.004	0.129± 0.003	0.138± 0.002	0.127 efg	0.060± 0.002	0.068± 0.001	0.073± 0.003	0.067 fg
Shehzadi	0.119± 0.004	0.136± 0.003	0.146± 0.003	0.134 de	0.063± 0.004	0.073± 0.001	0.078± 0.001	0.072 de
Ikra-3	0.095± 0.003	0.107± 0.002	0.113± 0.004	0.105 kl	0.050± 0.001	0.056± 0.001	0.060± 0.002	0.055 jk
Ikra-1	0.087± 0.003	0.096± 0.004	0.101± 0.003	0.095 m	0.049± 0.001	0.054± 0.002	0.057± 0.002	0.053 jk
Kiran-51	0.108± 0.002	0.123± 0.003	0.131± 0.003	0.121 ghi	0.058± 0.003	0.067± 0.001	0.071± 0.002	0.065 gh
Okra-7100	0.103± 0.002	0.116± 0.003	0.123± 0.002	0.114 ij	0.055± 0.002	0.063± 0.001	0.066± 0.001	0.061 hi
Sanum	0.116± 0.002	0.132± 0.002	0.141± 0.004	0.130 ef	0.063± 0.002	0.072± 0.001	0.077± 0.002	0.071 def
Lush green	0.113± 0.003	0.125± 0.003	0.134± 0.003	0.124 fgh	0.055± 0.001	0.063± 0.002	0.067± 0.001	0.062 hi
Ikra-2	0.099± 0.003	0.111± 0.002	0.117± 0.003	0.109 jk	0.052± 0.001	0.059± 0.002	0.062± 0.001	0.058 ij
OK-1305	0.114± 0.002	0.130± 0.003	0.139± 0.004	0.128 efg	0.061± 0.001	0.070± 0.001	0.075± 0.002	0.069 efg
OK-1307	0.091± 0.003	0.101± 0.004	0.106± 0.003	0.099 lm	0.048± 0.001	0.053± 0.001	0.056± 0.002	0.052 k
Pusasawani	0.145± 0.002	0.168± 0.002	0.183± 0.003	0.165 a	0.076± 0.002	0.089± 0.001	0.097± 0.003	0.088 a
MF-03	0.090± 0.002	0.100± 0.003	0.105± 0.004	0.098 lm	0.068± 0.002	0.075± 0.001	0.079± 0.004	0.074 cd
Okra-3	0.104± 0.004	0.118± 0.003	0.125± 0.003	0.116 hij	0.058± 0.001	0.066± 0.002	0.070± 0.001	0.065 gh
Click-5769	0.132± 0.004	0.153± 0.002	0.166± 0.003	0.150 b	0.072± 0.001	0.084± 0.003	0.092± 0.001	0.083 b
Mean	0.109 c	0.123 b	0.132 a	0.121	0.059 c	0.068 b	0.072 a	0.066

Table 10: Influence of high temperature stress on calcium and magnesium contents (ppm) of okra genotypes

Genotypes	Temperature Treatments							
	Calcium contents \pm S.E.				Magnesium contents \pm S.E.			
	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean	25 °C	40 °C	45 °C	Mean
Sabazpari	0.85 \pm 0.017	0.69 \pm 0.009	0.55 \pm 0.014	0.70 de	0.54 \pm 0.010	0.45 \pm 0.007	0.40 \pm 0.004	0.46 cd
Sarsabaz	1.06 \pm 0.021	0.90 \pm 0.011	0.72 \pm 0.012	0.89 a	0.57 \pm 0.012	0.47 \pm 0.011	0.42 \pm 0.009	0.48 bc
Pen beauty	0.79 \pm 0.011	0.63 \pm 0.014	0.51 \pm 0.017	0.64 gh	0.48 \pm 0.009	0.38 \pm 0.014	0.32 \pm 0.012	0.39 gh
Green wonder	0.76 \pm 0.014	0.59 \pm 0.014	0.49 \pm 0.016	0.61 hi	0.43 \pm 0.009	0.32 \pm 0.010	0.27 \pm 0.013	0.34 kl
Punjab selection	0.72 \pm 0.018	0.61 \pm 0.011	0.43 \pm 0.013	0.59 ij	0.45 \pm 0.010	0.35 \pm 0.008	0.29 \pm 0.012	0.37 ij
Anarkali	0.84 \pm 0.014	0.68 \pm 0.009	0.55 \pm 0.011	0.69 de	0.51 \pm 0.012	0.41 \pm 0.010	0.35 \pm 0.009	0.43 ef
Shehzadi	0.91 \pm 0.010	0.77 \pm 0.010	0.62 \pm 0.014	0.76 b	0.53 \pm 0.010	0.43 \pm 0.007	0.39 \pm 0.006	0.45 de
Ikra-3	0.79 \pm 0.012	0.62 \pm 0.013	0.50 \pm 0.010	0.64 gh	0.44 \pm 0.008	0.33 \pm 0.013	0.28 \pm 0.010	0.35 jk
Ikra-1	0.72 \pm 0.015	0.55 \pm 0.016	0.45 \pm 0.008	0.57 jk	0.33 \pm 0.007	0.25 \pm 0.012	0.20 \pm 0.015	0.26 m
Kiran-51	0.80 \pm 0.016	0.64 \pm 0.016	0.51 \pm 0.012	0.65 fgh	0.50 \pm 0.010	0.40 \pm 0.011	0.34 \pm 0.008	0.41 fg
Okra-7100	0.80 \pm 0.012	0.64 \pm 0.021	0.48 \pm 0.018	0.64 gh	0.47 \pm 0.009	0.36 \pm 0.009	0.31 \pm 0.011	0.38 hi
Sanum	0.85 \pm 0.010	0.70 \pm 0.011	0.56 \pm 0.14	0.70 d	0.53 \pm 0.011	0.43 \pm 0.014	0.38 \pm 0.009	0.44 de
Lush green	0.81 \pm 0.014	0.65 \pm 0.018	0.52 \pm 0.012	0.66 efg	0.48 \pm 0.008	0.38 \pm 0.007	0.33 \pm 0.010	0.40 gh
Ikra-2	0.74 \pm 0.012	0.57 \pm 0.013	0.46 \pm 0.018	0.59 ij	0.46 \pm 0.012	0.36 \pm 0.010	0.30 \pm 0.008	0.38 hij
OK-1305	0.89 \pm 0.012	0.74 \pm 0.009	0.59 \pm 0.015	0.74 bc	0.52 \pm 0.006	0.42 \pm 0.010	0.37 \pm 0.12	0.44 e
OK-1307	0.71 \pm 0.015	0.54 \pm 0.015	0.44 \pm 0.009	0.56 jk	0.42 \pm 0.009	0.31 \pm 0.014	0.26 \pm 0.011	0.33 kl
Pusasawani	0.93 \pm 0.018	0.78 \pm 0.021	0.63 \pm 0.010	0.78 b	0.59 \pm 0.010	0.49 \pm 0.013	0.45 \pm 0.008	0.51 a
MF-03	0.69 \pm 0.010	0.52 \pm 0.008	0.42 \pm 0.013	0.55 k	0.40 \pm 0.0110	0.30 \pm 0.012	0.24 \pm 0.007	0.31 l
Okra-3	0.84 \pm 0.012	0.68 \pm 0.013	0.54 \pm 0.008	0.69 def	0.47 \pm 0.007	0.37 \pm 0.010	0.31 \pm 0.012	0.38 hi
Click-5769	0.85 \pm 0.015	0.70 \pm 0.016	0.61 \pm 0.018	0.72cd	0.59 \pm 0.013	0.49 \pm 0.006	0.44 \pm 0.012	0.51 ab
Mean	0.82 a	0.66 b	0.53 c	0.67	0.49 a	0.38 b	0.33 c	0.40